

(Institute of Natural Products, Canary Islands, Spain) for the ir and pmr spectra of acetyl methyl pomolate (acetyl methyl benthamate). The financial assistance of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

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Triterpenoids from *Dillenia pentagyna*

K. P. TIWARI*, S. D. SRIVASTAVA

and

S. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad, U. P.Manuscript received 17 April 1979, revised 20 December 1980,
accepted 9 June 1981

DILLENIA pentagyna (Fam: Dilleniaceae) is a medicinal plant^{1,2} and has not been chemically investigated so far. Four triterpenes, lupeol, betulin, betulonic acid and morolic acid have been isolated from the stem bark of this plant and are reported here.

The air-dried powdered stem bark of *D. pentagyna* (2 kg) was extracted with EtOH under reflux for 25 days on a water bath. The extract (2.5 litres) was filtered off, concentrated to 100 ml and poured into H₂O (500 ml). The H₂O insoluble material was extracted with hexane and C₆H₆ respectively. The hexane soluble fraction on column chromatography over alumina gave two compounds called compound-A and compound-B. The C₆H₆ fraction on concentration gave a dirty white solid mass which was again extracted with petrol (60-80°) and CHCl₃ respectively and gave Compound-C and Compound-D.

Compound-A, on crystallization (MeOH : CHCl₃) furnished silky needles, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 213-14°. It gave LB test for triterpenoids, ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹ 3325 (OH), 1639, 1380 and 885. It was identified as lupeol by mixed m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with an authentic sample³.

Compound-B, crystallized as white needles from aq. EtOH, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442), m.p. 251-52°. It

gave the usual tests for triterpenoids, ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹ 3350 (OH). From the detailed study of its ir, ¹H nmr, ms and derivatives it was proved to be betulin⁴ which was further confirmed by co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen.

Compound-C was crystallized from EtOH as white needles, C₃₀H₄₆O₃ (M⁺454), m.p. 250-52° (d). It gave LB test and noller reaction for terpenoids, ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹ 3460, 1640, 1380, 880. It formed a monomethyl ester, m.p. 164-65° (Found; C, 79.50; H, 10.25; C₃₁H₄₈O₃ required; C, 79.48; H, 10.25%). Its ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃, δ , TMS) showed a signal at 3.60(s) for a carbomethoxy group. It formed a semicarbazone, m.p. 282-83° and an oxime, m.p. 236° (d). The identity of this compound with betulonic acid⁴ was established by mixed m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

Compound-D was crystallized from EtOH, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, (M⁺456), m.p. 272-73°. It gave LB test for triterpenoids. ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹ 3450, 1640, 804, 828. It formed an acetate (Ac₂O/Py, m.p. 255-57°; ν_{\max} 1740) and a methyl ester (CH₃N₂, m.p. 228-29°; ¹H nmr, CDCl₃, δ , 3.60 ppm, 3H) showing the presence of -OH and -COOH groups in the compound-D. It was identified as morolic acid⁵ by comparison of mixed m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, Dr. S. Silvavinayakam, CIBA—GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay for his kind help in micro-analyses and spectral data of the compounds. One of us (S.D.S.) is thankful to the State Council of Science and Technology, U.P., Lucknow for financial assistance.

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The Triterpenoid Constituents of the Leaves of *Nyctanthus arbortristis* Linn

A. S. R. ANJANEYULU, Y. L. N. MURTY,

and

L. RAMACHANDRA ROW

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair

Manuscript received 26 February 1981, accepted 9 June 1981

THE shrub *Nyctanthus arbortristis* Linn¹ (Fam: Oleaceae, Ver. name. Tel: Parijataka) is widely cultivated throughout India as a garden plant. Isolation of nyctanthic acid, a 3-4 secotriterpene

acid from the seeds²⁻⁴ and two flavonal glycosides⁵ astragalín (kaempferol-3-glucoside) and nicotiflorín (kaempferol-3-rhamnoglucoside) from its leaves and nycthanthíc acid from the heartwood of this plant were earlier reported. Our results on the reinvestigation of its leaves are presented in this note.

The leaf powder (1 kg) was successively extracted with n-hexane, ethylacetate and methanol. The wax free hexane extract on chromatography on neutral alumina⁶ yielded nycthanthíc acid (80 mg), m.p. 223-5°, [α]_D+81.5°, M⁺ 440, methyl ester, m.p. 125° and friedelin (75 mg), m.p. 255°, oxime, colourless plates m.p. 292-4°. The identity was established by comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the respective authentic specimens.

The detanned ethylacetate extract, on concentration left mannitol, m.p. 166°, hexaacetate, 125-6° and hexabenzooate, 149° and the residue on column chromatography on silica gel yielded β -sitosterol (100 mg), m.p. 135° and two more triterpenes, lupeol, m.p. 210° (50 mg) and oleanolic acid (125 mg) m.p. 310°, [α]_D+78° which were identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the appropriate authentic samples.

Present reinvestigation of the leaves of *N. arbor-tristis* reveals the presence of friedelin, lupeol and oleanolic acid in addition to nycthanthíc acid, the only triterpene reported by earlier workers. Further, the co-occurrence of oleanolic acid with the corresponding 3-4 seco acid, nycthanthíc acid is of biogenetic significance.

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Chemical Investigation of *Grewia populifolia* Vahl and *Phaulopsis parviflora* Willd*

K. S. MUKHERJEE, M. K. BHATTACHARYYA

and

P. K. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, West Bengal

Manuscript received 13 March 1981, accepted 9 June 1981

GREWIA *populifolia* Vahl [Syn: *Grewia tanax* (Forsk) Aschers], is a medicinally important plant of the family *Tilliaceae*¹. It is a much branched shrub found in Punjab, Sind, Rajputana and Western India, down to the Nilgiri Hills. Mucilage of the bark of *G. populifolia* is reported to have bactericidal activity and also to be used in the treatment of tuberculosis in hilly areas. Some work on

seeds², stem³ and stem bark⁴ of this plant has been reported. Results of chemical examination of the leaves of this plant, on which no phytochemical work has been done so far are reported here.

Phaulopsis parviflora Willd [syn: *Phaulopsis dorsiflora* (Retz) Santapau] is a prostrate closely branched perennial herb belonging to the family *Acanthaceae* occurring throughout India excepting north-western region⁵. Only the leaves of this plant has been investigated earlier⁶. A systematic chemical investigation of the whole plant was, therefore, undertaken and the results are reported.

G. populifolia: The air dried powdered leaves of *G. populifolia* were exhaustively extracted in turn with petroleum ether (60-80°), benzene and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silica gel. The petroleum ether (60-80°) eluate furnished a solid, m.p. 85-87°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3325, 1450, 1375, 1060, 720 and 718 cm⁻¹. It did not respond to Leibermann-Burchardt test for sterols and triterpenes and was identified as triacontanol by usual comparison (m.m.p; co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample.

Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (3:1) mixture afforded a solid which on crystallisation from petroleum ether (40-60°) furnished colourless granules, m.p. 82-83° and analysed for C₃₄H₆₈O₂ (M⁺, 508). It did not respond to Leibermann-Burchardt test for sterols and triterpenes nor did it give any colouration with tetranitromethane. The compound in its ir spectrum exhibited absorption peaks at 3320 (OH), 1710 (Carbonyl), 1460, 1370, 725, 715 (aliphatic long chain) and 1066 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretching of secondary hydroxyl group) and formed an amorphous acetate, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720 cm⁻¹, on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine, and a diol, m.p. 71-73°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3300 cm⁻¹ on reduction with LiAlH₄ in THF.

The nmr spectrum (90MHz, CDCl₃) of the compound recorded signals at δ .90, 6H (2CH₃), 1.25, 52H (26CH₂), 1.75, 4H (2 CH₂, β to >C=O), 2.30, 4H (2CH₂, α to >C=O and around 4.00, 1H (-CHOH) indicating it to be a straight chain saturated aliphatic hydroxy ketone.

Further elaboration of the structure of this hydroxyketone has been possible from the mass spectral study. The mass spectrum of the compound recorded peak at m/e 509 (M+1) as expected for unsymmetrical ketones⁷. The other significant ion peaks appeared at m/e 353 (α -fission to carbonyl group), 183 (α -fission to carbonyl), 368 (McLafferty), 213 (α -fission to hydroxyl group), 198 (McLafferty) and 325 (α -fission to hydroxyl group).

All the above data conclusively show that the compound is tetratriacont-21-ol-12-one (I) and appears to be a new one

* Accepted for presentation at NASOC-V, Calcutta.